

Optimizing Artificial Lighting System for Indoor Farming Using Genetic Algorithm

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Abstract— Indoor plantations are part of urban plantations which are currently an alternative to urban plantations, the narrowness of agricultural land creates indoor plantations. The concept of urban plantations is not oriented to mass production results, but to a form of food security. The main problem that arises from indoor plantations is the lighting system. Through this research are expected to be able to make a more optimal lighting system using a genetic algorithm. The results of this study are two segments, namely the optimization of the lighting system is only effective for plants with the age group of seedlings and growth, optimization is not achieved in blooming session and further research is needed.

Keywords— *Indoor Farming, Artificial Lighting, Genetic Algorithm, Smart System*

I. INTRODUCTION

Artificial lighting has long been used in agricultural technology. The existence of this artificial light allows us to be able to grow plants in dark places or that are not exposed to sunlight, including indoors. To get a strong and fertile plant, it requires at least 10 to 14 hours of light exposure per day. [1] Accelerated photosynthesis occurs when the light received is in low levels, and the leaf size is relatively small compared to the size of the plant. Therefore, light with low intensity is very beneficial for the growth of leaf shoots and plant shoots, because it can increase the speed of photosynthesis. This has been used as research by a Canadian researcher.

There are many journals that have researched this artificial light. Most of the journals are specialized in agriculture or agrotechnology. The focus of the research focuses on the state of plants and the effects of artificial light on various types of plant species. One of them is research conducted by Rakutko, et al. He conducted detailed research on the properties of plants given various light spectrums. As a result, each plant species has a different need for light for optimal growth. In tomato plants, for example, the effect of adding blue LED light makes tomatoes produce more chlorophyll pigment. In cucumber plants, the addition of blue light is much more beneficial than in tomatoes, because cucumbers do need to produce a lot of chlorophyll for their leaves and fruit. [2]

However, there are many types of plants, so it takes a lot of experimentation to determine what levels and types of light are most needed for these plants. Therefore, we need technology that can facilitate solving the problem of which light is useful for different types of plants. This is where machine learning algorithms: genetic algorithms come into play. Genetics Algorithm (GA) is a computational method inspired by the natural selection process. [3] This algorithm uses computational techniques iteratively, until it finds a suitable solution to the problem. [4]

GA can be used to solve the problem of which type and intensity of light a plant needs. In the process, there will be repeated computations (selection, crossover, mutation, and replacement) until the loop condition stops being triggered.

In its own process, GA generates a lot of data that must be classified. This classification aims to find the pattern of light and the appropriate type of plant so that the longer it takes, the faster it will solve the problem. [5]

Therefore, this paper aims to find the optimal configuration of artificial lighting for lettuce plants. The scope of this experiment is primarily to build multiple supervised machine learning classifiers on a grow light data set and analyze the accuracy between these classifiers. The classifiers used in this experiment are support vector machine (SVM), decision tree (DT), and neural network (NN). Each classifier will be given the same dataset without the selection feature and with the selection feature. Feature selection will be done statistically, to make it easier for machine learning to classify. The accurate performance of each classifier will be compared statistically. Therefore, we can determine which machine learning classifier is good in this case.

II. RELATED WORKS

S. Yu. Efremova, et al. [6] In research on Modelling the effect of artificial lighting on plant growth, they are conducted research on modeling on artificial lighting effects and their impact on the development of collisions. Types of lamps used include a GLP-FH-56-B lamp, a GLP-FH-56-R lamp, and a GLP-FH-56-RB lamp.

The result from the study obtained is that there are several growth variations depending on the spectrum

received by the leaves. The results also explained the correlation between the lamps and the electrical load used during the lighting process. In this study, no optimization process has been carried out on the configuration of artificial light, namely distance, light intensity and optimal wave spectrum based on the age range of plants.

Chiara Piovene, et al. [7] in research of Optimal red:blue ratio in led lighting for nutraceutical indoor horticulture. The research explains that lighting using the right ratio between the composition of the red and blue spectrum will produce better plant weight mass, the ratio referred to in the range 0.7-5.5 in the second spectrum ratio light. This study resulted in the optimization of the optimal lighting composition.

III. EXPERIMENT DATASET AND METHODS

A. Dataset

This study uses a dataset taken through the measurement process in the instrumentation process using a lux meter sensor and camera. The variables measured were light intensity and leaf surface length. Measurement of light intensity aims to determine the response of plants to the amount of light intensity based on the age group of the plant, as well as to obtain an optimal configuration based on the color composition based on the ratio of the three types of lamps used, namely LED type lights Red LED, LED Blue, LED Far Red, LED full Width Spectrum.

The leaf length measured to determine the growth of plants and variety is *Bak Coy* or Brassicaceae type. The samples taken were six plants in one box. These data sources also supported by several environmental indicator like soil moisture and temperature around the plant. When the beginning of the measurement on October 5 2022 to November 15 2022.

The authors took a random sample of four data classification which is the first group at the age of plants 0 to 7 days, the second group was at the age of plants 7 to 14 days, the third group was from 14 to 21 days, and the fourth group at 21 to 33 days of age. In this observation, the authors also focuses on collecting data in the morning and evening in the range of dates mentioned earlier.

B. Methods Specification

The method used in this study uses a genetic algorithm with function optimization based on evolutionary optimization, taking a population sample which one converted into *x-chromosomes* and *y-chromosomes*. This method is used to find optimal settings related to the configuration of artificial lighting so that the growth of bak coy plants can grow indoors and without getting lighting from sunlight.

GA (Genetic Algorithm) looks for the best results by carrying out the fitness process repeatedly until it finds a generation that meets the specified conditions.[8] The process carried out is to match the chromosomes in the form of a vector and is determined by the position of the gene (the value of the vector), each row of data will be exchanged with the genetic code called crossover. In biology, marriage is an

exchange of genes in the chromosomes that will be inherit to the child. Figure 1 below shows how genes are exchanged in the chromosomes and find optimum results.

Fig. 1. Genetic Algorithm Flowchart

Not all vectors have partners, the term mutation is used to exchange genetic code in vectors that do not have partners. Important step is to determine the most optimal generation of genetic exchange results for each chromosome or vector. The GA method in this research used to determine the most optimal settings for each configuration with two variables, namely the height of the LED lamp placement and the intensity of the light. We assume that L is the symbol for the amount of light intensity data and H is the amount of hardware placement height data, so in a formal language it can be written as follows:

$$\begin{cases} L = \{H_j\}, j = \overline{1, m}, H = \{A_i\}, i = \overline{1, n} \\ L_j = \{h_j^y\}, y = \overline{1, w_j} \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

C. Methods Requirement

The requirements for setting the observed light spectrum are listed in the following table:

TABLE I. LIGHT SPECTRUME

No	Color Spectrum	Wavelength	Frequency	Photon Energy
1	Violet	380-450nm	668-789 THz	2.75-326 eV
2	Blue	450-495nm	606-668 THz	2.50-2.75 eV
3	Green	495-570nm	526-606 THz	2.17-250 eV
4	Yellow	570-590nm	508-526 THz	2.10-2.17 eV
5	Orange	590-620nm	484-508 THz	2.00-2.10 eV
6	Red	620-750nm	400-484 THz	1.62-2.00 eV

Fig. 2. Active Radiation Area for Photosynthesis

The need for light spectrum in the four age groups under observation is shown in table II below:

TABLE II Light Spectrum for Age Group Classification

No	Group	Spectrum Color	Ages Range	Height of Light
1	Seed Sprout	Red	0 – 7	100 cm
2	Plant Growth	Red+blue	7-21	50 cm
3	Adult Plant	Red	21-27	25 cm
4	Flowers Bloom	Red+Blue	27-33	20 cm

Fig. 3. Height of Light Configuration

Boxes or plant placement boxes are designed to support the flexibility level of lighting, the design is as shown in Figure 4 below:

Fig. 4. Box Design

IV. RESULTS AND ANALYSIS

In this research, we will look at the results of the configuration and methods for finding an optimal solution for artificial lighting systems and the results of these settings implemented in indoor urban farming. The results of the arrangement are based on a genetic algorithm. The implementation of the GA method is shown in the pseudocode below:

1. Create randomly population P of $Popsiz$ Individuals
2. **While**(stop_condition) FALSE
3. $P^* = \emptyset$
4. **While** (Sizeof(P^*) $\neq Popsiz$)
5. Select P_1 and P_2 from P
6. CrossOver P_1 and P_2 to obtain h_1 and h_2
7. Mutate h_1 and h_2 to obtain c_1 and c_2
8. **If** ($Dis(p_1, c_1) + Dis(p_2, c_2) \leq (Dis(p_1, c_2) + Dis(p_2, c_1))$)
9. **If** $c_1 < p_1$ **then** $P^* = P^* \cup \{c_1\}$ **else** $P^* = P^* \cup \{p_1\}$
10. **If** $c_2 < p_2$ **then** $P^* = P^* \cup \{c_2\}$ **else** $P^* = P^* \cup \{p_2\}$
11. **Else**
12. **If** $c_1 < p_2$ **then** $P^* = P^* \cup \{c_1\}$ **else** $P^* = P^* \cup \{p_2\}$
13. **If** $c_2 < p_1$ **then** $P^* = P^* \cup \{c_2\}$ **else** $P^* = P^* \cup \{p_1\}$
14. **Endwhile**
15. $P = P^*$
16. **Endwhile**

A. Hardware Assembling and Implementation

The hardware is assembled according to the design model in Figure 4, designed using PVC (Polyvinyl chloride) material with an LED support frame, the assembly process is shown in Figures 5 and 6 below:

Fig. 5. Assembling Actuator Procedure

Fig. 6. Assembling Sensor Calibration

Testing of the artificial light system is carried out when the light intensity reaches 0 ~ 10 Lux and checks the age of the plants. In the calibration process, the resulting light

is violet, which refers to the most optimal configuration for the age group 0 to 7 days.

Fig. 7. Calibration Light Intensity

Fig. 8. Inside to Indoor Plantation system

Light intensity measurement data taken over a span of 33 days, divided into four age groups with altitude-based settings alternated between age groups.

TABLE III. LUX MEASUREMENT AVERAGE

Lux Measurement				
Age Groups	Light Distance			
	100cm	50cm	25cm	20cm
First Group	1735.714	2490	2941.429	4184.714
Second Group	1730.714	2490	2947.143	4098.786
Thrid Group	1735	2495	2960	3928.75
Fourth Group	1730	2487.778	2944.444	4050.889

B. Programming

Based on the results of this study, the microcontroller needs to find the appropriate configuration based on the age range of the plants. The search procedure uses a genetic algorithm to find the most optimal value based on the reading of the lux meter sensor, the data entered is based on the input leaf width and light intensity received.

TABLE IV. LEAF LENGTH MEASUREMENT

Age Groups	Leaf Length			
	100cm	50cm	25cm	20cm
First Group	5.00			
Second Group		7.67		
Third Group			13.32	
Fourth Group				16.66

Fig. 9. Leaf Length on 33 Days

Using test sample data, the average value of leaf growth and the number of intensities needed by each group, random samples are then processed using a genetic algorithm using the Python programming language for optimal light height, the following results are found:

TABLE IV. OPTIMAZION LIGHT SYSTEM RESULT USING GENETIC ALGORITHM

FG	SG	TG	FG
103.4348	48.37681	23.89855	20.50725

Fig. 10. Leaf Length prediction using genetic algorithm

V. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORKS

Based on the test results on the optimization system using a genetic algorithm, the conclusions from the results of this research are two important things:

1. Optimization of light height is only optimal in the age group 0-7 days and 7-14 days
2. Optimization of light height in the age group 14-21 and 21-33 will experience a decrease in growth when using recommendations from the results of genetic algorithm calculations due to decreased light intensity.

The authors recommends conducting further research regarding the accuracy of plant responses to light intensity and radiation resulting from the release of photon energy in artificial light.

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